

Joan DeHovitz was born in St. Louis, Missouri. As a young child she moved to Palo Alto, CA. Years after, her family moved to San Francisco, where she attended Lowell High School. She holds a B.A. Degree in Mass Communications from the University of California, Berkeley (Cal).

After completing the educational process, in 1984 she started working at the Bank of America in San Francisco, but resigned that position in 1989, before the birth of her first child. During the 90's, she gave birth to her four children, and dedicated her time raising them and managing a busy household.

Starting in 2008, Joan acted as a parent representative in various capacities at the Branson School in Ross, CA. She was also responsible for organizing a wide range of functions for up to 250 people.

Joan DeHovitz began serving as a board member at the Community Health Resource Center (CHRC) at the California Pacific Medical Center in 2011.

Joan DeHovitz specializes in event management, event organization, planning, hosting and customer service. Namely, Joan has successfully planned a number of events, ranging in size from 20 to 250 guests, including budget, vendor management and contract negotiations. She has led and acted as event host to insure the needs of all guests/attendees were accommodated.

Additionally, she has completed many training programs of Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction (MBSR), such as the Professional Teacher Training Program including the MBSR Fundamentals Practicum at El Camino Hospital in Mt. View, CA. Joan also completed an 8 week MBSR introductory course at UCSF Osher Center with James Mitchell. She is on the teacher training path of Mindfulness-based Stress Reduction (MBSR), affiliated with The Center for Mindfulness at UMass Medical School.

Joan will participate in the Practice Teaching Intensive (PTI) Retreat in Petaluma, CA in the spring of 2018, and upon completion, she will be certified to lead MBSR sessions.